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Infrastructure Spending for Cleanup of Illegal Dumping in Duncan and the Calgary Water System

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Abstract

There is an ongoing need to rebuild infrastructure around the world, and this article describes how the Canadian military could be involved in three examples at various scales. As the Canadian government increases military spending to reach NATO targets, it is possible to consider new types of capabilities for the military, such as the ability to build or repair infrastructure. This article proposes a scénario where we create military capability to build infrastructure for three scenarios: one example is in Ukraine, where the military makes specialized concrete; another example is the City of Calgary, where the military repairs the drinking water system; and the third example is to clean up illegal dumping at the Cowichan Tribes territory on Vancouver Island. The article discusses the costs in terms of the infrastructure itself and the organizational costs for the military to develop these new capabilities.

Keywords: Military, GDP, NATO, Infrastructure, Canada, Ukraine, Cement, Calgary, Water, Cowichan, Illegal Dumping, Landfill, Remediation, Pollution, Environmental

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P11 - Planning, Coordination, and Reform
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There is an ongoing need to rebuild infrastructure around the world, and this article describes how the Canadian military could be involved in three examples at various scales. As the Canadian government increases military spending to reach NATO targets, it is possible to consider new types of capabilities for the military, such as the ability to build or repair infrastructure. This article proposes a scénario where we create military capability to build infrastructure for three scenarios: one example is in Ukraine, where the military makes specialized concrete; another example is the City of Calgary, where the military repairs the drinking water system; and the third example is to clean up illegal dumping at the Cowichan Tribes territory on Vancouver Island. The article discusses the costs in terms of the infrastructure itself and the organizational costs for the military to develop these new capabilities.

The Canadian government has increased total planned spending on the military to meet the NATO target for 2% of GDP in 2026 (Cléophat & Kho, 2025). The Government of Canada increased military spending by \$9 billion for 2026, with the majority of the increase going to the Department of National Defence and \$0.6 billion to Other Government Departments. The Parliamentary Budget Office notes that the total planned spending by the Department of National Defence is \$48.1 billion, and Other Government Departments is \$14.6 billion in 2026. How much of this spending is used for unconventional capabilities, like infrastructure development?

The Canadian military needs infrastructure to operate, so there is a rationale for it to be able to build infrastructure. The Canadian military can use this capability to build infrastructure for military or civilian needs of allies, such as Ukraine. The Canadian military could start producing equipment and materials in Canada, then transport and use them in Ukraine for applications like specialized additives to help make concrete stronger. The military could mine the additive in Canada, process it, bring it to Ukraine, and use it with customized mobile concrete production circuits. The military could also reinforce the supply chain in Ukraine by helping produce raw materials like aggregates, cement, water, and chemical additives required for cement in the country as a way to use military spending for development goals.

The second idea for military involvement with infrastructure is to repair the drinking water system for a large city. The rationale for this idea is that access to water is essential for safety and wellness. Without clean water, there is a risk of disruption to law and order beyond what a regular city police force can handle, and there is potential for a crisis that may require military help. For example, the drinking water system in the City of Calgary had a catastrophic failure in 2024 that cost approximately \$40 million to fix and will require additional work:

“The cost for the repair of the initial break and repair of 29 additional pipe segments was about \$38.2M... The City of Calgary experienced a catastrophic break on the Bearspaw South Feeder Main on June 5, 2024. This feeder main is the largest in Calgary’s network, and it distributes a significant portion of the city’s treated water supply. This break was repaired in June 2024, along with five additional “hot spots” that were discovered. In August/September 2024, additional repair work was carried out on 21 segments along the feeder main. On October 16, 2024, three additional segments of the Bearspaw South Feeder Main were repaired.”
The City of Calgary (2024).

The water system represents essential infrastructure for the city and may represent an issue of national security in extreme scenarios. It would be unprecedented for the Canadian military to get involved with the drinking water system in a Canadian city, but they could potentially provide a quick response to this major problem that has cleanup costs beyond local capacity.

I believe it is worthwhile to generate the necessary skill sets within the military to do all aspects of the project, rather than hiring contractors. Also, the military could prioritize using Canadian equipment and materials to fix the problems; if the gear is not available, then the military could start to make it themselves. This would be a brute-force solution by the federal government that would likely cost much more than if the City of Calgary fixed it themselves, because it requires the government to build new capabilities to do the work. This would not be the lowest cost approach to fix this infrastructure problem, but it could be a quick way to fix the

problem in a comprehensive way beyond what the local city can afford. The military could provide a way to help coordinate federal funding for local problems that are too big for locals to handle.

In 2024, the City of Calgary spent \$40 million to fix problems with the water system. Will they face another \$40 million of costs in 2026? What is the total cost to fix the entire system? For example, it could cost \$200 million over 2 years to fix the entire drinking water system. And it could cost the military another \$300 million in organizational costs to develop the capabilities to do the work. This could be a \$500 million spending program for the military over 2 years, which would be approximately 1% of the total military budget of \$61 billion. Would this be a good use of military spending?

A small-scale example of infrastructure spending is to clean up illegal dump sites on the Cowichan Tribes' territory. The rationale for getting the military involved here is that these are potentially serious instances of pollution that require immediate and comprehensive cleanup. We can coordinate the legal responsibility among First Nations governments, local cities, the province, and federal agencies after these sites are cleaned up to prevent them from happening again, but the priority now is to clean up these sites immediately.

Recent media coverage describes how the government is currently taking a wait-and-see approach to these sites:

“A technical report, ordered by the provincial government, confirmed that the waste pile has asbestos in it and that pollutants are leaching into the groundwater and migrating downstream. The City of Duncan confirmed on Thursday that its drinking water wells are downstream from the dump, and while they are concerned about the situation, they believe there is no current risk to the water.” (Judd & Johnson, 2025)

The financial statements from Cowichan Tribes (2025) mention contaminated sites as follows. They do not know how many contaminated sites are on their territory, and they do not know the cost to clean them up, so they set the liabilities at zero. For example:

“There are numerous potential contaminated sites on the reserve. The future costs of remediation are undeterminable and a reasonable estimate cannot be made. The liabilities, if any, and related recoveries will be recorded when they become measurable.” (Cowichan Tribes, p. 22, 2025)

The Cowichan Tribes provide a further description of how to measure the economic liability of contaminated sites as follows:

“A liability for remediation of a contaminated site is recognized at the best estimate of the amount required to remediate the contaminated site when contamination exceeding an environmental standard exists, the Nation is either directly responsible or accepts responsibility, it is expected that future economic benefits will be given up, and a reasonable estimate of the amount is determinable. The best estimate of the liability includes all costs directly attributable to remediation activities... As of March 31, 2025, no liability for contaminated site exists.” (Cowichan Tribes, p. 22, 2025)

The Cowichan Tribes records the liabilities for these when they become measurable; how do we make these sites measurable? One way is for the Cowichan Tribes to hire consultants to estimate the cost for cleanup and use that amount as the liability, but they are not doing that. Another way to make the contamination measurable is through the courts; the Cowichan Tribes is suing the regional district and the federal government to recover costs it incurred for landfill closure and post-closure expenses.

“Cowichan Tribes incurred landfill closure and post-closure expenses and has commenced litigation against the Cowichan Valley Regional District ("CVRD") to recover costs associated with remediating the reserve from contamination. The CVRD has filed a Statement of Defence. In addition, a separate claim has been filed against the CVRD and the Government of Canada for contamination of the reserve. This second claim was served on the parties, and the Nation is engaged in settlement negotiations with the

CVRD to settle both claims. The recovery will be recorded once the lawsuit has been settled.” (Cowichan Tribes, p. 22, 2025)

Will the courts determine that the governments owe the Cowichan Tribes for cleanup costs? Do the governments have any ability to be involved in the cleanup if they pay for it? What changes are being made to ensure that more contamination does not happen in the future? The Cowichan Tribes do not describe the closure and post-closure expenses amounts, but we can estimate them based on disclosures from other levels of government: they are around \$10,000 to \$20,000 per year in direct costs for environmental monitoring at a single abandoned landfill site, as described below.

The Cowichan Valley Regional District (2024) financial statements include the total amount for Landfill Obligation of \$480,960 for three contaminated sites. They write, “*Although the CVRD does not operate an active landfill site, the Regional District is responsible for four former landfills, three of which are associated with old Thermal Reduction Plants (TRPs or municipal solid waste incinerators).*” The CVRD post-closure costs include groundwater monitoring and average \$10,000 to \$20,000 per year for 20 years. The CVRD assumes a \$0 liability for the contaminated site on the Cowichan Tribes' territory, which is the subject of the lawsuit mentioned above.

There is no accounting for the actual cleanup costs as described in the financial statements from the Cowichan Tribes or the CVRD. Depending on the scale of the contamination, neither the Cowichan Tribes nor the CVRD may be able to do this kind of cleanup themselves. The annual financial statements from Cowichan Tribes (2025) note that they spent \$1 million on repairs and maintenance in 20205, but this may not be enough to clean up a large contaminated site.

For example, the illegal dump site on Cowichan Tribes territory may contain 300,000 cubic metres of waste (Judd & Johnson, 2025). This could be approximately 810,000 tonnes at a specific gravity of 2.7x. The total cleanup costs could range from \$100 to 1,000 per tonne for digging, removal, and containment or cleanup. With these assumptions, the total cost to clean up

this one site could range from \$81 million to \$810 million. This is more than the Cowichan Tribes or the CVRD could immediately pay for.

The Cowichan Tribes' (2025) financial statements show cash of \$121 million in 2025 and \$42 million in 2024. The annual program expenses total \$92 million in 2025, where the top three items comprise 60% of total expenses: salaries and benefits are \$35 million, tuition and student expenses are \$11 million, and contracted services are \$10 million. The total funding by Indigenous Services Canada is \$93 million in 2025, which was approximately \$25 million larger than the 2025 budget or the 2024 actual amount. The Revenue from the Province of British Columbia is \$10 million. In 2025, the accounts payable were \$12 million, and the long-term debt was \$7 million. There was a large increase of \$80 million in cash from \$42 million in 2024 to \$121 million in 2025, but this was offset by a decrease of \$35 million in non-cash working capital based on decrease in advance receivables from \$30 million in 2024 to \$9 million in 2025 and decrease in term deposits from \$25 million in 2024 to \$9 million in 2025.

The Cowichan Tribes has a relatively low coverage ratio for total expenses on an annual basis, with cash on hand of \$121 million versus annual expenses of \$92 million. The revenue from Indigenous Services Canada and the Province appears to be large enough to cover the annual expenses, which suggests that most of the Cowichan Tribes' cash is available for discretionary purposes. For example, they could start a comprehensive program to identify all contaminated sites on their territory and measure the cleanup costs to include them in the financial statements. The total accumulated surplus of \$239 million for the Cowichan Tribes represents a substantial accumulation of capital; however, they do not have enough cash on hand to cover total cleanup costs that may range from \$81-810 million themselves. By using the military to clean up this site, the government can create new ways to expedite projects that otherwise appear to fall in between the responsibilities of various levels of government.

The military can find new ways to build capabilities that are essential to their mission, while also having indirect beneficial impacts on communities in need at home and abroad.

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